

BUSINESS CULTURE IN POST-INDUSTRIAL SOCIETY AND ITS REPRESENTATION IN MODERN ENGLISH LITERATURE

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Abstract. *The goal of this research article is to identify the substance and function of business culture within the late 20th-century cultural and historical backdrop, as well as how business culture is understood in literature, particularly business-related novels, which offer a distinctive means of illuminating the various business culture categories.*

Keywords: *business, management, business culture, society, international society, international management, post-industrial society.*

INTRODUCTION

Business is expanding internationally due to recent developments in the globalised world, and it is more important than ever to investigate cultural diversity and consider its advantages for international management. Problems of a cultural type are strongly associated with a growing interest in business culture, its role in society, and various international societies. It is necessary to analyse the current state of business culture because subjectivism in the perception of culture and its components, and consequently, subjectivism in the assessment of an organization's culture by its employees, may differ significantly from the perception of business culture by society, the state, clients, or other entities.

Basically, the only scientific field that allows one to approach the problem of analysing business culture and its main categories—like "international management" and "organisational culture" in post-industrial society—from the perspectives of multiple disciplines—such as psychology, economics, sociology, management, history, philosophy, and linguistics—is anthropology. The ability to thoroughly identify the issues that an organisation faces, forecast short- and long-term conditions at the international, national, and organisational levels, and identify solutions for social responsibility, international management, and business ethics are all made possible by the cultural approach.

This article aims to ascertain the nature and function of business culture within the late twentieth-century cultural and historical backdrop, as well as how business culture is understood in literature, particularly business-related novels, which offer a distinctive means of illuminating the various business culture categories.

Using scientific information from multiple domains, an interdisciplinary method is used to investigate the main categories of corporate culture in post-industrial society. Specifically, we consult basic sciences like history, philosophy, and cultural studies. We also consider and actively utilise management information from the management discipline.

METHOD

Using scientific and fictional English-language literature as an example, the study is based on a thorough interdisciplinary analysis of the categories of business culture ("organisational culture" and "international management") in the cultural and historical context of the late 20th century.

The following methods were used to solve the research problems:

the diachronic analysis method, which is required to examine the evolution of the concept of organisation from the perspective of organisational culture inherent in a specific stage of development of society;

the axiological method for examining the value orientations of an organisation, group, or individual;

the modelling method, which employs the idea of organising an organization's culture's constituent parts to form its overall picture;

a method of interpretation that enables us to pinpoint the primary traits of global management and organisational culture in a particular literary work;

a method for cultural-contextual analysis that enables us to ascertain how a work relates to its historical and cultural setting;

a comparative approach that makes it possible to analyse artistic creations in order to comprehend the concepts of "international management" and "organisational culture";

a method for linguocultural analysis that allows one to discern deeper levels of meaning inside a literary work and to understand the cultural context that underlies the correlation between language's surface structures and underlying cultural meanings.

RESULTS

1. In a post-industrial society, corporate culture is aggressively taking centre stage across multiple domains of society and becoming increasingly significant on its own.

2. Taking into account both internal and external components at the "national – global" level in international management, the model of "organisational culture" that is presented is based on an interdisciplinary approach and enables us to systematically analyse the organisational culture of any organisation.

3. A breakdown of the category "international management" demonstrates the distinctions between national and global business models, the importance of international management in creating a strong organisational culture, and the necessity of considering the cultural aspect of this process.

4. A new trend in contemporary English-language literature, the business book of the late 20th century reveals the fundamentals of the various business culture categories in a post-industrial society.

5. A late 20th-century literary work about business, or business novel, is a cultural phenomenon that combines the domains of psychology, morality, and aesthetics in the context of individual living.

6. The business novel's problem domain highlights the national traits of business management culture implementation that have emerged in English-language literature.

7. The author's opinions on the corporate culture of a post-industrial society can be put into practice through a business fiction.

8. A contemporary author illustrates the impact of organisational culture on the development of the primary character and the influence of cultural elements of the global business environment on the sociocultural conflict between "individual - business" in a literary work about business as a cultural phenomenon.

9. Serious issues with the organization's survival and ability to adapt to the outside world arise from the cultural divide between the levels of organisational culture (stated ideals and fundamental concepts) and their execution.

10. Examining the category "organisational culture" in contemporary business novels enables us to pinpoint the function of organisational culture in the processes of social globalisation and the related divergence-convergence processes, in selecting a business model, and from the perspective of international and domestic business ethics.

DISCUSSION

The study, "Linguocultural and Sociocultural Features of the Novels by I. Banks "The Business" and D. Grisham "The Firm" in the Context of Business Culture," attempts to analyse business novels as artistic texts with multifaceted meanings and implicit, indirect information about the nature of business relations, the influence of the organization's culture on the individual, and society at large. Thus, identifying the essence and essential characteristics of the text and establishing a link between it and the historical period it reflects are crucial to the success of interpretation.

The function of the title, the usage of managerial jargon, and the theme of money are taken into consideration in this cultural analysis of the novels themselves. The title is the first character in the work and is situated outside the main body of the text. I.R. Galperin claims that the title refers to "the compressed, undisclosed content of the text." It can be compared, symbolically, to a bent spring that unfolds to reveal its capabilities[1].

The title functions as a special version of the main image in each of the novels. The title of Grisham's book "The Firm" alludes to a business theme that permeates the entire work. The plot of the story is explained in the title, which does not specify the time or location of the event. It seems sense for the reader to assume that the "firm" will serve as both the novel's primary personification and symbol. The title takes on a characteristic of generalisation as the narrative progresses and becomes a symbol of the common. A scenario where a "company" manifests as an inverted organisation, a symbol of a destructive utopia that separates a person from an unfamiliar organisational culture, and a business setting that dehumanises him and incites conflict at the "individual-organization" level are all typified by the author in this book.

Similar to the novel "The Firm," in "The Business," the author's interpretation of the global model is made clear through the gradual disclosure of the title's general meaning as well as the expansion and enrichment of the term "business" semantics. "The Business" refers, strictly speaking, to a company or multinational enterprise that is fundamentally more potent than certain states. "We have a sufficient amount of compromising evidence on almost everyone and everything, be it commercial enterprises, sovereign states or major religions," the main character says in explaining the success of "The Business" organization [2].

Therefore, the expression of ethical judgment—which is a common theme in Banks' works—is linked to the text's dominating idea. A second cultural reading of the term "business" gives rise to the idea of the "silent takeover" [3] in international management, which denotes a few dominant corporations gaining significant influence over the entire globe. As a result, the title of the novel "Business" conveys the sociological as well as the economic relevance of international management, company, and the individual in the process of continued globalisation.

Organisational culture as the primary instrument of international management is the central theme, and its growth and interpretation are based on an analysis of the theme of money in business fiction. We can also gain a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of the author's perspective on the late 20th-century global commercial landscape thanks to this analysis.

Since money is seen as an oblique symbol of social membership in the worlds of the affluent and poor, it serves as the foundation for the social interpretation of the major struggle in the works rather than having an economic one. For this reason, the issue of money in novels has more social than economic relevance. The writers of the novels under review present the issue of money as a feature of the end of the twentieth-century worldwide culture as well as the American one. This theme, which is depicted in the novels' everyday aspects, will be fully explored in their dramatic depth, making the issues of need-poverty and the meaning of the deaths of numerous young, gifted people in the face of enormous sums of money held by international corporations and mafia organisations more pressing. These novels' sharply posed issue of capital and money takes on the depth and personality of a gripping social tragedy as it develops.

Through their composition on the subject of money, the writers elucidate the ideas of "international management" and "organisational culture." A system of economic law governing the allocation of money is in place in the first chapters of the book "The Firm," according to which labour, extreme professionalism, and diligence are all equivalent to money. Initially, terms like "work," "to economise on," "businesslike approach/efficiency," and "labour" (toil/labor) had positive implications in Mitchell McDeere's and the company's partners' values.

The novel's later chapters provide contrasting coverage of the theme's development: money is now seen as the equivalent of deception and crimes against the state rather than honest labour, and there is a system of money laundering (also known as the "money-laundering process") and other legal infractions like bribery, blackmail, and contract killings of individuals the organisation does not want, among other things. With money concentrated in the hands of mafia institutions and a few ambitious billionaires pursuing a programme of international expansion (the novel "The Business"), money therefore becomes a symbol of injustice and the erroneous structure of the world.

The primary literary characters' development is seen in both books. For Mitchell, the protagonist of the novel "The Firm," it is mutual understanding between close friends; for Katrin, the protagonist of the novel "The Business," it is the preservation of cultural values in the state of Tulane and the welfare of its residents. Essentially, what matters to them is not so much material as it is moral comfort.

The author particularly skillfully depicts a severe tension between the main character's moral issues and aspirations and the financial, commercial side of things in the book "The Business." I. Banks makes a logical connection between the phrase "to do the business," which means "to conduct business on a commercial basis, make transactions," and the name of the organisation, "The Business."

CONCLUSION

Finally, we came to the following conclusions:

1. The fundamental idea behind comprehending corporate culture is that, in a post-industrial world, it is inextricably linked to other spheres of culture.
2. The issue of "organisational culture" as the primary form of corporate culture and as a tool of "international management" is most thoroughly exposed within the framework of the contemporary cultural approach. In the literature of the second half of the 20th century, organisational culture is discussed from a scientific, practical, and cultural perspective.
3. We can emphasise the core characteristics of the category of international management by examining it within the cultural framework of issues with effective management of

organisational culture. International management has a global aspect, but it also necessitates consideration of the cultural influences imposed by the nation in which business dealings are conducted.

4. The application of linguoculturalology to the analysis of business novel texts enhances our comprehension of the fundamental ideas underlying the various business culture categories. It also enables us to discuss the business novel as a unique subgenre of late 20th-century English-language literature that reflects the current state of public consciousness. The analysis revealed that these novels, with their unique problems and imagery, provide a sufficiently thorough reflection of the business culture. This is important because it helps explain the national differences in business culture and the related issue of business ethics.

5. By applying the systemic model of organisational culture developed in this work to businesses featured in business novels, we can illustrate the detrimental effects of the discrepancy between the stated and actual values and norms of the organisation, highlighting the subjectivity of employees' perceptions of the business and the tension between the external environment and the organisation. Therefore, irregular growth of specific organisational culture components can lead to major issues with international management, the organisation itself, and the organization's ability to adapt to the outside business environment.

6. By applying a systemic model of organisational culture to examine the "individual – organisation" contradiction, we can illustrate how organisational culture shapes an individual's development. Thus, the nature of the main literary character's evolution is disclosed, and the conditions that lead to a conflict between an individual and an organisation are demonstrated. These conditions are predicated on the individual's acceptance or rejection of the value system that directs the organization's operations, rejected individual leaves the system.

7. The impact of globalisation on organisational culture is what defines international management at the "national – global" level. International business is ethically characterised by business fiction. Not only can business culture help to ease internal conflicts and improve social harmony within a company, but it should also play a role in the "global village" as a whole. In actuality, it frequently serves as a cover for the organization's actions, which are morally reprehensible.

8. The analysis of science and fiction literature reveals that in the post-industrial era, there are opportunities for cross-cultural communication and the inconsistencies between various national business models are resolved.

In general, the study's findings established that a novel about business, as a fresh approach to exposing the categories of business culture, not only reflects the key ideas of the concepts of business culture, which have been thoroughly examined by numerous scientific schools, but also demonstrates the fundamentals of business and adds a great deal of cultural context to the understanding of business culture's categories.

A relevant and exciting area of cultural studies research is the study of corporate culture in post-industrial societies.

REFERENCES

1. Galperin I.R. Text as an object of linguistic research. M., 1981, p. 133.
2. Banks I. Business. Novel. M., Eksmo Publishing House, 2004, p. 47.

3. Trappe T. Tullis G. *Intelligent Business, A Matter of Choice*. Pearson Education Limited, 2005, p. 19.
4. *The Core of Management. Marketing Management: A textbook for master's students at Moscow State University*. Lomonosov (co-author), M.: TEIS, 2002. 56 p.
5. *The culture of doing business in modern English-language literature // "Issues of cultural studies": Scientific, practical and methodological journal*: M.: Publishing House "Panorama", Vol. 12, 2008, p. 41–44